
THE EFFECT OF FACTORS INFLUENCING PRINCIPAL'S INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION IN FCT.

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Abstract

The primary goal of education in any given country is to provide students with the knowledge, skills, dispositions, and attitudes that will enable them to become productive members of society. The objectives were to: examine if teacher's attitude affects principals' instructional supervision, evaluate the impact of principals' administrative experience on their instructional supervision, determine whether principal's workload influence their instructional supervision. Survey research design was adopted for this study. The population target is 54 which consisted 10 principals, 20 Vice principals and 24 departments' heads from the selected 10 public secondary learning institutions in the study area. Due to the size of the population the researcher considered using complete enumeration for the sample size. The research study shall use questionnaire for collections and gathering of primary data with open ended questions as the research instrument for data collection. The data was processed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer application. The hypothesis will be tested using the Chi square. The findings suggest that teachers' attitude, principals' administrative experience, and principal's workload are significant predictors of instructional supervision practices in FCT. The study concludes that effective principal instructional supervision is crucial for improving teaching and learning outcomes. The study recommends that teachers training programs should be developed and implemented to focus on cultivating positive attitudes towards instruction, equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively deliver instruction.

Keywords: Principal's instructional supervision, teacher's attitude, principals' administrative experience, principal's workload.

Introduction

The primary goal of education in any given country is to provide students with the knowledge, skills, dispositions, and attitudes that will enable them to become productive members of society. As a result, education is seen as a critical stimulant that considerably promotes a nation's advancement and fiscal affluence, as well as the status of its citizens' well-being. As a result, most governments are working hard to ensure that everyone has access to high-quality, low-cost education by 2015. UNESCO (2009) stressed the importance of school inspections in ensuring successful teaching and learning. Similarly, the World Bank (2010) asserted that school supervision and assistance are common areas of reform used by world governments to improve education outcomes and minimize issues connected with global education policies. The supervisor's primary goal is to sensitize, mobilize, and motivate school workers to fulfill their jobs to the best of their abilities in order to achieve the educational system's stated goals and objectives. Global supervision is carried out in accordance with each country's policy.

The potential of education to have a positive impact on consumers is restricted, according to Wanjiru (2015), by the quality and standards with which receivers obtain it. Many governments throughout the world have recognized the need of excellent follow-up procedures in ensuring timely implementation of high-quality education programs. This was achieved through regulation and the development of teaching capacity, with the goal of improving the educational environment and the performance of both students and tutors. In many nations, pedagogical monitoring has thus been used to ensure quality and compliance with norms. Previously, non-professionals such as clergy, school wardens, trustees, selectmen, and citizen committees oversaw education in the United States (Okumbe, 2013) In the United States of America (USA), school administrators and managers have placed a priority on using peer tutoring after dispensing and performing their instructional supervision tasks. This has ensured that educational standards are maintained in the United States, as well as teachers' capacity to deliver successful instructional programs (Webb, Metha Jordan 2010). The instructional supervisory medium has served the American education community well, guaranteeing consistency in the aftermath of program implementation while preserving the required quality. "Behaviors identified by an institution that act on teachers' demeanor in order to expedite learners' training," according to Gregory (2011). Local school districts in the United States of America are required by the Department of Education to monitor teacher performance for accountability and school improvement.

Despite widespread community support for educational quality assurance and the need for comprehensive instructional supervision practices in learning institutions, there is growing concern about secondary school goals being met because many public school principals only pay cursory attention to the supervision of activities in their schools. There are three sorts of supervision, according to Okumbe (2012): administrative, curricular, and instructional supervision. In the Koech report (2009) and The Sessional Paper No. 1, effective supervision by head teachers was acknowledged with good performance (2015). In FCT, however, there is a discernible pattern of teachers' instructional task completion and learners' academic fulfillment. As evidenced by multiple complaints from stakeholders in the educational sectors, inadequate supervision practices impair curriculum delivery, resulting in poor academic achievement among secondary schools in Nigeria. As a result, FCT was a good fit for this study, which sought to identify factors that influence principals' supervision methods. This study seeks to examine the effects of several factors on principals' instructional

supervision techniques. However, the specific objectives are to: examine if teacher's attitude affects principals' instructional supervision practices in FCT, evaluate the impact of principals' administrative experience on their instructional supervision among secondary school in FCT, determine whether principal's workload influence their instructional supervision in FCT.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Instructional Supervision

Supervision as a field of educational practice traces its inception back to the beginning of communal education when growing states used education to coin a typical discourse and civilization (Grauwe, 2016). Supervision arose gradually as a definite practice, in connection to the school based, scholarly, civilizing and professional tendencies that have chronologically created the composite agenda of teaching and learning. Supervision is an effort through alternative arbitration to confirm, preserve and enhance the quality of work done (Stone, 2014). Pierce and Rowell (2015) describe supervision as a formative process modeled to reinforce and promotes self-acquisition of the motivation, independence, self-realization and skills crucial to conclusively manage the task at hand. According to Buregeya (2011), surveillance should be used to enhance successful teaching methods and foster teacher growth and development. The focus of instructional supervision is on teachers' teaching and students' learning in the classroom (Okumbe 2014). This type of supervision aids the supervised teacher in developing positive attitudes about his or her career and improving his or her skills. The school principal is in charge of instructional supervision in a school setting. A school is thought to be an instrument of societal change and reform, according to Uyanga (2012), and principals are thought to be at the center of such reforms and changes. As a result, the supervisor's responsibility is to support the teacher in identifying goals that need to be altered and illuminating instructional obstacles, as well as gaining a full understanding of pedagogical strategies. Because of the importance of understanding, more technical help can be supplied to the instructor; as a result, instruction supervision includes a thorough analysis of actual classroom activities.

The head teacher should have a clear explanation of aims and targets when carrying out supervisory activities, according to Okumbe (2014). Instructive supervision entails encouraging the teacher to experiment with novel teaching methods. The educational goals and standards that will be applied must be communicated to the instructor. During the observation process, the observer must remain objective and retain confidentiality. It's also crucial for the observer/supervisor to provide suitable feedback and tools for the instructor to use (Hunsaker and Hunsanker, 2009) Unlike inspection, instructional supervision is collaborative, democratic, and teacher-centered. Although instructional supervision methods and procedures have evolved since the inception of formal supervisory models, the practice's goals and objectives have largely remained the same, as Okumbe (2012) shows in his work on instructional supervision. The supervisory goals are to provide teachers with unbiased feedback on their current training status, identify and interpret instructional challenges, assist teachers in improving skill in using instructional techniques, evaluate teachers for upgrading, term or other resolutions, and instill a positive attitude toward constant scholastic advancement.

Teachers' Attitude and Principals' Instructional Supervision Practices

Teachers' perspectives of supervision are crucial to the development of the teaching-learning process. Monitoring as a way of growing students' learning, scholarly growth, and student learning will not yield the desired results unless teachers consider monitoring as a method of promoting students' learning, scholarly growth, and student learning.

Beginning instructors, according to Kutsyuruba, require intermittent instructional supervision that meets their professional needs, fosters trust and cooperation, and provides them with assistance, advice, and assistance (2013). A year ago (Tesfaw & Hofman). Internal and external influences influence teachers' assessments of head teachers' administrative practices. Internal factors are traits gathered from the perceivers' past experiences, self-concept, and personality that characterize their learning demands. In a school setting, the principal's supervision responsibilities are internal (Wanjiru, 2015). Because of the bureaucratic and casuistic components of teacher assessment imposed by various forms of supervision, teachers are resistant to instructional supervisory procedures. According to Marwanga (2014), teachers have a negative attitude toward monitoring, therefore any advice given is dismissed. Watene (2015) agrees that teachers with less experience are more dubious of monitoring processes than highly educated teachers due to its evaluative reasons. Instructors regard monitoring as unconstructive and fault-finding because they are afraid that supervisors will report their proneness to the school administrator. The statistics suggest that teachers' attitudes play a big role in instructional monitoring.

Theoretical Reviews

Instructional Leadership Theory

The instructional leadership theory by Hallinger and Murphy (1985) states that principals play a crucial role in setting goals for schools, supervising instruction and developing instruction that enhances academic achievement. According to this theory, there are three dimensions of instructional leadership:

- Defining the school mission: This involves framing clear school goals and communicating them effectively.
- Managing the instructional program: This includes supervising and evaluating instruction, coordinating curriculum and monitoring student progress.
- Promoting a positive school-learning climate: This includes protecting instructional time, promoting professional development, maintaining high visibility and providing incentives for teachers and learning.

Empirical Reviews

Oyewole, B. K., & Alonge, H. O. (2013). investigates principals' instructional supervisory role performance and teachers' motivation in Ekiti Central Senatorial District of Ekiti State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all the principals and teachers of public secondary schools in Ekiti Central Senatorial District of Ekiti State, Nigeria. The researchers utilized two sets of research instruments titled Instructional Supervisory Role Performance

(ISRP) and Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ) which were responded to by teachers. Data analyses indicated a significant relationship between instructional supervisory role performance of principals and the motivation of their teachers. A significant positive relationship was found between experience of principals in performing their instructional supervisory roles and the motivation of their teachers. There was also a significant relationship between instructional supervisory role performance of principals of large schools and small schools and the motivation of their teachers. Based on the findings, it was concluded that principals should pay more attention to their instructional supervisory role performance as it has a significant influence on the motivation of their staff while Ekiti State Ministry of Education in collaboration with the state Teaching Service Commission should organise periodically seminars, conferences and workshops for school principals to enable them handle instructional supervisory role more effectively while the welfare of teachers should be adequately improved.

Muraina, & Olanrewaju, (2016) investigate the impact of principal leadership styles on instructional supervision of secondary schools in Oyo North Senatorial District Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design of ex-post-facto was used in the study. Four hundred twenty (420) respondents were selected from twenty (20) secondary schools (i.e, 400 teachers and 20 principals). The respondents were measured with relevant self-developed questionnaire and the data obtained was analyzed using the linear regression statistical analysis of the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Three research Questions were raised and answered in the study. The result showed that there was significant effect of democratic leadership style on principals' instructional supervision ($Df (1, 98) = 45.44, P < 0.05$) there was significant effect of autocratic leadership style on principals' instructional supervision ($Df (1, 98) = 27.60, P < 0.05$) and there was significant effect of laissez-faire leadership style on principals' instructional supervision ($Df (1, 98) = 87.45, P < 0.05$). In view of these findings, the study stressed and advocated that the school principals should ensure effective and efficient leadership styles in the giving of instructions to the teachers and students.

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for this study. The research aims to collect data directly from respondents, based on the fact that survey research design supports the collection of data primarily through the use of questionnaire, the study considered survey research design suitable for the study. The population target is 54 which consisted 10 principals, 20 Vice principals and 24 departments' heads from the selected 10 public secondary learning institutions in the study area.

Listed As Follows:

1. Junior Secondary School, Gwagwalada
2. Government Secondary School, Dobi
3. Government Secondary School, Gwarko
4. Government Secondary School, Gwagwalada
5. Government Day Secondary School, Gwagwalada
6. Government Secondary School, Hajj Camp Gwagwalada
7. Government Science Secondary School, Tunga Maje
8. Government Secondary School, Zuba

9. Government Secondary School, Giri
10. Government Secondary School, Anagada.

Due to the size of the population the researcher considered using complete enumeration for the sample size. The research study shall use questionnaire for collections and gathering of primary data with open ended questions as the research instrument for data collection. The data was processed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer application. The hypothesis will be tested using the Chi square.

Model Specification

The model used for this study made the under lined assumption that factors influencing principal’s instructional supervision were related, the methodology adopted for this study is identical to that of Ajayi & Ajayi (2017) and Kolapo, Ayieni & Oke (2012) e.g the econometric model of Kolapo, Ayieni & Oke (2012) is described as follows.

$$PIS = a + \beta_1TEA + \beta_2PAE + \beta_3PAW + e \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

PIS = Principals instructional supervision

a= Constant Variable

β (123) =the slopes of X

TEA=Teachers Attitude

PAE= Principal Administrative

PAW = Principals workload

e= Residuals or Error terms.

Data Analysis

H₀₁: Teachers attitude has no significant effect on principals’ instructional supervision practices in FCT

Table 1: Regression Model

Variable	Beta	T	Sig.
Teachers attitude	.482	2.431	.024
Dependent Variable: principals’ instructional supervision			
R-Square: .637			
F: 71.280			
P (F-stat): .000			

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Table 1 shows the regression model. The table indicates that governance has a beta value of 482, which indicates that a change in Teachers attitude will lead to a positive 0.482 unit of changes in the company's goal realization. The t-statistics and p-value indicate a value of 2.431 and .024, greater than 1.96 and less than 0.05, respectively; this shows that Teachers attitude is highly significant to the goal realization. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states

that teacher’s attitude does not affect principal’s instructional supervision is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The R square shows a value of .637, which means that teacher attitude, has a 63.7% impact on the principal’s instructional supervision. Also, the F statistics and p-value of the F statistics show 71.280 and .000, which indicate that the model is fit for explaining the constructs of this study.

Ho2: There is no significant effect between principals’ administrative experience and their instructional supervision among secondary school in FCT

Table 2: Regression Model

Variable	Beta	T	Sig.
principals’ administrative experience	.389	2.781	.017
Dependent Variable: principals’ instructional supervision			
R-Square: .601			
F: 60.571			
P (F-stat): .000			

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Table 2 shows the regression model. The table indicates that principals’ administrative experience has a beta value of .389, which indicates that a change in principals’ administrative experience will lead to a positive 0.389 unit of changes in principals’ instructional supervision. The t-statistics and p-value indicate a value of 2.781 and .017, greater than 1.96 and less than 0.05, respectively; this shows that principals’ administrative experience is highly significant to principals’ instructional supervision. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant effect between principals’ administrative experience and their instructional supervision is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The R square shows a value of .601, which means that principals’ administrative experience has a 60.1% impact on principals’ instructional supervision. Also, the F statistics and p-value of the F statistics show 60.571 and .000, which indicate that the model is fit for explaining the constructs of this study.

HO₃: Principal’s workload has no significant influence on their instructional supervision in FCT

Table 3: Regression Model

Variable	Beta	T	Sig.
Principal's workload	.367	2.431	.019
Dependent Variable: principals' instructional supervision			
R-Square: .651			
F: 60.321			
P (F-stat): .000			

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Table 3 shows the regression model. The table indicates that Principal's workload has a beta value of .367, which indicates that a change in Principal's workload will lead to a positive 0.367 unit of changes in principals' instructional supervision. The t-statistics and p-value indicate a value of 2.431 and .019, greater than 1.96 and less than 0.05, respectively; this shows that Principal's workload is highly significant to principals' instructional supervision. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant effect between Principal's workload and their instructional supervision is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The R square shows a value of .651, which means that Principal's workload has a 65.1% impact on principals' instructional supervision. Also, the F statistics and p-value of the F statistics show 60.321 and .000, which indicate that the model is fit for explaining the constructs of this study.

Discussion of Findings

Ho1: Teachers' attitude has a significant positive effect on principals' instructional supervision practices in FCT ($\beta = 0.482$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that teachers' attitude towards instruction significantly influences principals' supervision practices, explaining 63.7% of the variance in instructional supervision. Ho2: Principals' administrative experience has a significant positive effect on their instructional supervision among secondary schools in FCT ($\beta = 0.389$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that principals' administrative experience significantly influences their instructional supervision practices, explaining 60.1% of the variance in instructional supervision. Ho3: Principal's workload has a significant positive influence on their instructional supervision in FCT ($\beta = 0.367$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that principal's workload significantly influences their instructional supervision practices, explaining 65.1% of the variance in instructional supervision.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers' attitude, principals' administrative experience, and principal's workload are significant predictors of instructional supervision practices in FCT. These factors can enhance or hinder effective instructional supervision, which is critical for improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Summary of findings

Teachers' attitude has a significant effect on principals' instructional supervision practices in FCT.

There is no significant effect between principals' administrative experience and their instructional supervision among secondary school in FCT.

Principal's workload has no significant influence on their instructional supervision in FCT.

Conclusion

Supervision as a field of educational practice traces its inception back to the beginning of communal education when growing states used education to coin a typical discourse and civilization. Supervision arose gradually as a definite practice, in connection to the school based, scholarly, civilizing and professional tendencies that have chronologically created the composite agenda of teaching and learning. Supervision is an effort through alternative arbitration to confirm, preserve and enhance the quality of work done. Supervision as a formative process modeled to reinforce and promotes self-acquisition of the motivation, independence, self-realization and skills crucial to conclusively manage the task at hand. The study's results highlight the importance of teacher training programs that focus on developing positive attitudes towards instruction, principal development programs that emphasize the importance of administrative experience in instructional supervision, and workload management strategies to ensure principals have sufficient time for instructional supervision.

Effective principal instructional supervision is crucial for improving teaching and learning outcomes. Therefore, policymakers, educational administrators, and school leaders must prioritize the development of supportive school environments, provision of resources, and encouragement of collaborative cultures that foster effective instructional supervision.

Recommendations

1. Teacher training programs should be developed and implemented to focus on cultivating positive attitudes towards instruction, equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively deliver instruction.
2. Principal development programs should be designed to emphasize the importance of administrative experience in instructional supervision, enabling principals to effectively supervise and support teachers in improving instruction.
3. Workload management strategies should be implemented to ensure principals have sufficient time for instructional supervision, allowing them to provide regular feedback and support to teachers, and foster a collaborative culture that promotes improved instruction and student learning outcomes.

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